

MDMC

Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

Implementation of FAIR data in
Transient Absorption
Spectroscopy and
Photoluminescence Spectroscopy

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I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in EuroFEL Support Laboratory, CNR-ISM - Roma Tor Vergata.
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“Not bad for a girl with no talent.”

Kim Kardashian

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Choosing to enroll in this Master’s program was driven not only by curiosity—as I boldly claimed while staring dramatically at the audience gathered in the Aula Magna at SISSA in late October 2024, but also - let’s be honest - by a FAIR dose of recklessness. It has been a long and sometimes uphill journey, filled with unexpected turns, steep learning curves, and more than a few moments of doubt. But despite the challenges, I have never regretted taking this path. On the contrary, it has been one of the most enriching and transformative experiences I could have hoped for. First and foremost, I wish to thank the EuroFEL Support Laboratory group —Stefano Turchini, Daniele Catone, Giuseppe Ammirati, Alessandra Paladini, Patrick O’Keeffe and Francesco Toschi — for their guidance, insightful feedback, and patience. I am also deeply grateful to all the members of the Area Science Park and SISSA team, especially Federica Bazzocchi, Mariarita de Luca and Tommaso Rodani for their assistance and constructive suggestions during both the lecture period and the laboratory internship. A big thanks to my fellow Master’s students, especially the Spectroscopy group, for sharing both the triumphs and the struggles of programming. From staring blankly at the screen together to celebrating when the code finally worked (for about 5 minutes), I couldn’t have asked for a better group to suffer—and occasionally succeed — with. Finally, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my family for their unwavering support, love, and patience throughout this adventure: thank you for not disowning me when I told you I was leaving my job to pursue this Master — you probably thought I was joking at first, but I wasn’t. Your patience and belief in my questionable decisions were essential for me to get through it all. Last but not least, a special thank you to Guy De Roquefeuil, who somehow managed to come out of this whole ordeal unscathed, despite living with me. Whether it was listening to me vent about my latest coding disaster, or reassuring me that no, the Universe was not conspiring against me, you’ve been there every step of the way. I truly couldn’t have asked for better support.

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Abstract

This thesis explores the implementation of FAIR data principles — Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability — within the context of the spectroscopy experiments conducted at the EuroFEL Support Laboratory. The project focuses on the adoption of the NeXus data format to adapt the output data from the Femtosecond Transient Absorption Spectroscopy and Photoluminescence Spectroscopy beamlines. For the transient absorption setup, the existing LabVIEW acquisition system was adapted to include the required metadata structures defined by the NXoptical_spectroscopy application definition. In parallel, a graphical user interface was developed to convert proprietary `.spc` files into NeXus format for photoluminescence measurements. All files generated were tested for cross-platform interoperability and FAIR compliance using open-source visualization tools. This work contributes to the standardization and transparency of scientific data workflows, supporting long-term goals of Open Science as outlined by international initiatives such as FAIRmat and UNESCO.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Open Science: a revolutionary paradigm shift

In the essay “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions” [1] Thomas Kuhn discusses the nature of scientific progress introducing for the first time the concept of “paradigm” within epistemological debate. The word “paradigm” derives from the greek *paradèigma* and means “example”, “model”. According to Kuhn a paradigm in a scientific context is a set of rules, models and assumptions that scientists use to tackle problems and interpreting data. Kuhn argues that progress in science is not achieved in a linear way. The path of scientific discovery, in fact, is often unpredictable and marked by challenges, anomalies and occasional crises. In this framework, the paradigm plays a crucial role in helping scientists address these challenges—until, inevitably, it no longer does. Kuhn individuates two phases in the development of science: the first phase is defined “normal science”, while the second is known as “scientific revolution”. During the phase of normal science, the work of the scientists is confined in the boundaries of an accepted paradigm and is aimed to reinforce the existing framework. However, when the unresolved anomalies encountered accumulate over time reaching a critical mass, crises arise and the paradigms adopted until that moment are no longer able to fulfill their function. And here it is the core of Kuhnian vision: the emergence of crises and the collapse of frameworks induce a paradigm shift, that is a radical transformation redefining the previous assumptions. The paradigm shift is, therefore, the spark that ignites scientific revolution. In the light of Kuhn’s arguments, Open Science can be considered as a paradigm shift that challenges the traditional framework. But what is, in practice, Open Science? The adjective Open may immediately be evocative of a contrast with a close

world. However, the reality is far more complex than this because defining Open Science is not a trivial task. The term itself can be considered as an umbrella concept that describes a broad range of practices and principles aimed to increase the quality and the transparency of research, to promote the sharing of results and to foster collaboration between scientists of various backgrounds. At the same time the term Open Science individuates an entire cultural movement committed to advocating for these practices. The Unesco Recommendation for Open Science (UROS) [2], published in 2021, is the result of a collective institutional effort aimed at redefining the very ethic of scientific inquiry. In this document are presented four core principles underlying the vision of Open Science, making it of pivotal importance in the further development of scientific research:

- Open Scientific Knowledge
- Open Science Infrastructure
- Open Engagement of Social Actors
- Open Dialogue with other knowledge systems

Open Scientific Knowledge, as stated in the UROS, “refers to open access to scientific publications, research data, metadata, open educational resources, software, and source code and hardware that are available in the public domain or under copyright and licensed under an open licence that allows access, re-use, repurpose, adaptation and distribution under specific conditions, provided to all actors immediately or as quickly as possible regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status or any other grounds, and free of charge. It also refers to the possibility of opening research methodologies and evaluation processes”. To achieve this objective, various strategies can be employed. For instance, researchers can choose to publish their work in journals that adhere to Open Access policies. Additionally, data and supplementary materials such as supporting information can be shared on platforms such as Zenodo, Figshare or Dryad, allowing the other members of scientific community to reuse them. Another effective mean for achieving Open Scientific Knowledge is the publication of preprints - the papers that have not yet undergone peer-review - on specialized platforms such as ArXiv. The advantage of this approach is that the peer-review process is expedited as scientists can directly interact with the material submitted, providing an immediate feedback. When discussing Open Science Infrastructure, we refer to shared

structures, both physical and digital, that support open science and facilitate access for citizens and the broader scientific community. These infrastructures include open laboratories, digital platforms, and repositories, such as GitHub, that enable collaboration, transparency, and the open sharing of research data, code, and findings. The engagement of social actors, that is - the involvement of people beyond the scientific community - is fundamental in order to promote scientific awareness and is also a valuable instrument for the research itself. In fact, the so-called “citizen science” - the research conducted by non-professional scientists following valid methodologies, can significantly contribute to scientific advancements by providing valuable data and encouraging collective problem-solving. In this way, the realm of science is no longer considered inhospitable and hostile, but becomes an important part of society nurturing the development of an informed and aware citizenry. The last principle, the dialogue with other knowledge systems, refers to the recognition of the contributes due to different cultural backgrounds, knowledge systems and epistemologies. As stated in the UROS, it focuses on the promotion and the “ inclusion of knowledge from traditionally marginalized scholars and enhance inter-relationships and complementarities between diverse epistemologies, adherence to international human rights norms and standards, respect for knowledge sovereignty and governance, and the recognition of rights of knowledge holders to receive a fair and equitable share of benefits that may arise from the utilization of their knowledge”. While the philosophy and the principles of Open Science offer a valid alternative to traditional scientific models, the process of its implementation is not immediate. Building on Thomas Kuhn’s epistemological vision, the birth of a new paradigm is typically met with resistance from the scientific community. In a similar fashion, Open Science practices encounter numerous obstacles stemming from cultural, social, and institutional factors. Within the academic sphere in particular, the academic reward system—which plays a crucial role in shaping scientists’ career trajectories—continues to favour publications in high-impact, subscription-based journals. Consequently, although Open Science presents concrete opportunities, many researchers, especially those at the early stages of their careers, have a reluctant approach towards it because there are concerned that adhering to this new paradigm may compromise their professional advancement. A further challenge lies in the risk of widening the gap between researchers in high-income countries—who, at least in principle, benefit from greater access to financial resources and infrastructure supporting Open Science—and their counterparts in marginalized contexts, who may lack the means to participate on equal footing. Equally significant is the issue of “open-washing”, whereby institutions and publishers adopt the language and rhetoric of openness without a genuine commitment to its

values, thereby reducing Open Science to a mere branding strategy. In conclusion, the paradigm shift represented by Open Science extends well beyond methodological concerns: it demands a profound reconfiguration of the relationship between science and the broader socio-cultural context in which it operates.

1.2 Aim of the work: implementation of FAIR principles for transient absorption spectroscopy and photoluminescence spectroscopy

The EuroFEL Support Laboratory, located in CNR-Istituto di Struttura della Materia in Rome, is one of the facilities integrated in the NFFA-DI project network. The NFFA-DI project is intended to lay the foundation for a solid research infrastructure connecting various facilities across Italy involved in materials science. One of the project's defining features is the implementation of the FAIR principles aimed at enhancing the quality of the research and fostering the cooperation between institutions and scientists. The scientific activity of the laboratory is devoted to pump-probe ultrafast spectroscopy. The spectroscopy of excited states is crucial for the study of excited states that play a key role in photovoltaic cells, in photocatalytic materials, plasmonic nanostructures, transport properties, elastic properties, and semiconductor optoelectronic devices. The laboratory is equipped with an ultrafast and tunable-in-wavelength laser source funded by NFFA-DI, a spectrometer for Fast Transient Absorption, and a spectrometer for luminescence with laser diode source to perform steady-state and time-resolved photoluminescence. In this thesis work, within the framework of both the Master in Data Management and Curation and the NFFA-DI project, I developed the implementation of FAIR principles in the two main beamlines of the EuroFEL Support Laboratory: the transient absorption spectroscopy beamline and the photoluminescence beamline. The data generated by the instruments has been made compliant with the FAIR standard through the development of NeXus data format files.

1.3 Thesis Outline

The thesis is organized in five chapters which aim is to address and explain the various aspects of the work. In Chapter 2 are illustrated the theoretical framework of the FAIR principles and the NeXus data format. Chapter 3

introduces the foundations of the spectroscopic techniques employed in the laboratory with an experimental case of study. In Chapter 4 is described the experimental setup of the EuroFEL Support Laboratory focusing on the characteristics of the beamlines involved. Chapter 5 illustrates the workflow and the development of the technical solutions adopted to manage the instrumental data output according to the FAIR principles along with the issues encountered during the process. In Chapter 6 are discussed the results and the future perspectives for the adoption of FAIR principles in research infrastructure.

Chapter 2

FAIR principles: Theoretical Framework

In light of recent technological advancements, a comprehensive reassessment of the entire research infrastructure has become imperative. As is widely recognized, reproducibility of results constitutes one of the fundamental pillars of scientific practice. However, the discourse surrounding reproducibility necessarily entails a redefinition of the paradigms associated with data reuse within the scientific domain, as well as the definition of good data management—particularly in the context of the emerging role of artificial intelligence technologies. The formalization of these evolving paradigms was first articulated in 2016, with the publication of the seminal article “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” (Wilkinson et al.)^[3]. This article is the result of a joint effort by multiple stakeholders from diverse sectors—including academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers which aim was to establish a set of guidelines to facilitate the effective management and reusability of scientific data. But what does FAIR mean in this context? FAIR is an acronym that stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. These four principles effectively encapsulate the foundational concepts underlying this new approach to scientific data. Notably, the FAIR principles are not designed solely as guidelines for human interpretation, but also explicitly for machine readability. In fact, one of the central objectives of this collective effort is to promote machine-actionability—that is, the ability of computational systems to autonomously find, access, interoperate with, and reuse data with little to no human intervention. It is also important to highlight that the FAIR principles apply not only to data itself, but also to the processes used to generate, analyze, and manage that data—such as algorithms, workflows, and tools. Furthermore, it must be emphasized that these principles were

conceived as high-level guidelines: they do not prescribe specific technical implementations or enforce particular standards, thereby allowing for flexibility across different scientific domains and technological contexts. In the following section each principle will be explored in detail[4] [5], pointing out its distinctive characteristics and practical implications with respect to scientific data management.

2.1 F-Findable

A digital resource is defined findable if it can be easily retrieved by humans or computers. To achieve this, it is fundamental to have extensive machine-actionable metadata that enable the automatic discovery of dataset and services. Before delving deeper in the implication of this principle, it is important to give the definition of data and metadata in the FAIR context. The term data refers to all types of digital resources—not only to data in the strict sense, but also to elements such as software and other digital artifacts. Conversely, the term metadata refers to the information that enables the discovery, reuse, interpretation, or assessment of a particular digital resource.

Findability in the FAIR context is ensured by adherence to the following conditions:

- F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. Data are described by rich metadata
- F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describe
- F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

The *leitmotiv* of these conditions is the concept of unambiguity. In fact, each identifier must have a one-to-one correspondence with a unique digital resource - this is the essence of “globally unique”. Moreover the identifier must be persistent, which means that it continues to identify the same resource even if the latter is no longer available. An example of identifier that meets these conditions is the DOI, Digital Object Identifier, that incidentally satisfies also the A2 sub-principle (see. Par 1.2). The presence of a rich set of metadata accompanying the data is another factor that addresses ambiguity. In fact, the more thoroughly an object is described by an abundance of metadata—treated according to the F4 principle—the more findable and unambiguous it will be.

2.2 A-Accessible

Accessibility of resources is achieved by implementing clear and standardized protocols—both for humans and machines—that govern the retrieval of digital resources. Additionally, it involves defining transparent and well-documented procedures for obtaining access to protected or restricted data.

As a corollary of this principle:

- A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
- Sub-principle A1.1. the protocol is open, free and universally implementable
- Sub-principle A1.2. the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A3. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Communication protocols are defined as a set of rules that allow the exchange of data between two or more entities in a consistent and predictable manner. An example of a communication protocol is the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). Sub-principles A1.1 and A1.2 specify the conditions that a communication protocol must meet. Specifically, it should not present any obstacles to the retrieval of digital objects, regardless of whether the access to the resource is restricted or not. In the event that the data are no longer available, it is essential to preserve the accessibility to metadata in order to provide context and an understanding of the data nature and provenance. When discussing Accessibility, it is also essential to point out that within FAIR context to be accessible does not mean to be “open”. The sub-principle A1.2 addresses this distinction, as there are situations where data and metadata may be restricted due to ethical, legal or contractual considerations.

2.3 I-Interoperable

If a machine is able to integrate information from two or more digital resources within the same domain—thereby generating a more comprehensive and cohesive understanding—then the condition of interoperability is considered to be met. Conversely, the same machine should also be capable of recognizing compliance and facilitating interaction between data and software tools, particularly when a digital entity is processed by an online service. To

support such interactions, it is essential to establish a well-defined semantic framework for all entities involved.

Following the interoperability principle, we have the subsequent set of conditions:

- I.1 (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
- I.2 (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I.3 (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

It is clear from these points that the concept of interoperability is intertwined with the machine readability of data and metadata and, subsequently, with the need of a language that should be formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable, as illustrated in [5].

2.4 R-Reusable

The reusability of digital resources is achieved when those resources are so thoroughly characterized and well-described that even a machine is capable of performing decision-making processes—such as determining whether and under what conditions the resources can or should be reused, and identifying the appropriate entities to credit for their use.

- R1 (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- Sub-Principle R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
- Sub-Principle R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
- Sub-Principle R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

At first glance, the R1 condition may appear similar to F2 (see Par. 1.1), but its underlying rationale is different. While the F2 condition focuses on enabling effective attribute-based search and query (findability), the purpose of R1 is to allow both machines and humans to assess whether a discovered resource is appropriate for reuse in a specific task. The issue

of under which conditions it is possible to reuse a set of data and metadata is addressed in sub-principle R1.1. As stated in "Introduction to FAIR data principles" (fairmat-nfdi.eu) "license clearly outlines terms and conditions for data reuse and ensures that users know what they can and cannot do with the data". Sub-principles R1.2 and R1.3 address the issues of provenance and compliance with domain-specific community standards. Using a metaphor from forensic analysis, establishing the "chain of custody" for data and metadata—that is, having comprehensive records of their origin and history—ensures that they are both reusable and aligned with the standards required for their reliable interpretation and application.

Box 2 | The FAIR Guiding Principles

To be Findable:
 F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
 F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
 F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
 F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:
 A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:
 I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
 I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:
 R1. (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Figure 2.1: The FAIR principles at a glance[3]

2.5 NeXus Data Format

Among the various tools available for implementing FAIR data principles, the NeXus Data Format represents a valuable option. As reported in "The NeXus Data Format" (Könnecke *et al.*)[6], the idea of developing a file format capable of organizing scientific data in a structured way arose from the efforts of an international group of scientists, whose goal was to define a common format for data exchange and archiving in neutron, X-ray, and muon experiments. At its core, the Nexus Data Format addresses two key needs: the first is serving as a container for all the experimental data generated at a specific beamline, the second is providing well defined structures and standards for raw and processed data.

2.5.1 Technical Aspects of NeXus Data Format

The NeXus Data Format is built on top of HDF5 format (Hierarchical Data Format). This latter is widely used in scientific contexts due to its main feature that - as its name suggests - it is its ability to provide a hierarchical structure suitable for organizing complex, large and heterogenous datasets. The choice of HDF5 format was not dictated solely by the advantages of its hierarchical structure. It was chosen, in fact, also because it is in the public domain, supported by commercial and free software tools and because it is efficient, self-describing and platform-independent. HDF5 format can be thought as a file system resembling the one used in most computer operating systems. It consists, in fact, of folder-like elements called groups and file-like elements called datasets. The groups can contain datasets or even other groups, while the datasets consist in the actual data stored in the HDF5. NeXus enhances the HDF5 format by introducing a consistent framework of semantic and structural conventions. As detailed in the file documentation¹, this includes:

- a set of designing principles
- a set of data storage objects
- a set of subroutines
- the support of a scientific community committed to the improvement of the format and to the exchange of ideas and advices

At the core of every NeXus file are four fundamental building blocks: Groups, Fields, Attributes, and Links. Groups are directly derived from the group system of the HDF5 format and retain the same function as containers for fields and other groups. Fields, represented by HDF5 datasets, can be either scalar values or multidimensional arrays. Their size can range from 1 byte to 8 bytes, and their type can be integer, float, or character. Additional information can be attached to groups or fields using Attributes, while Links are used to reference the same information in different locations within NeXus file. A powerful feature of NeXus data format is the use of Class Types. Class Types, which name starts with the prefix 'NX', define the expected structure and content of the Field that a Group should contain. Example of classes include: NXentry, which is mandatory for a valid NeXus file, NXdata, NXsample and NXinstrument. NXentry represents the top-level group of a NeXus file and contains all the data, groups and classes related to the

¹<https://manual.nexusformat.org/introduction.html>

experiment under analysis. NXdata groups are designated to contain all the experimental data, both raw and processed, in a way that enables to generate directly plots or other visual representations. While NXsample contains all the information related to the sample, the group with the class NXinstrument encloses all the technical specifications of the instrumental setup allowing to describe it in detail. Since an instrument can have a plethora of features and components, each of them can be described by a separate group. Figure 2.2 clearly illustrates the logic behind the designing principles: on the left is shown an example of a NeXus data file containing information about two experimental runs. The two NXentry groups encapsulate the other groups and fields required to describe each run. The tree-like structure of the file is also highlighted. On the right, a detailed view of the NXinstrument group is presented, displaying all the subgroups corresponding to the individual components of the experimental equipment.

(a) NeXus representation of two experimental runs

(b) Structure of NXinstrument class

Figure 2.2: The hierarchical structure of a NeXus file. [7]

2.5.2 NeXus Application Definitions

Given that every scientific experiment entails a high level of specificity with respect to instrumentation, methodology and other aspects, NeXus provides a criterium that allows to define the format also for the most peculiar instrumentations. As stated in the NeXus format official documentation[7]: “the set of data storage objects is divided into three parts: base classes, application definitions, and contributed definitions. The base classes represent a set of components that define the dictionary of all possible terms to be used with that component. The application definitions specify the minimum required information to satisfy a particular scientific or data analysis software interest. The contributed definitions have been submitted by the scientific community

for incubation before they are adopted by the NIAC or for availability to the community.”

2.5.3 Compliance with FAIR principles

As stated in the previous paragraph, among the key features of NeXus data format there are its hierarchical structure that allows to archive and organize large datasets with their metadata and the use of a specific dictionary of terms and community-maintained definitions. These aspects make the NeXus format an ideal candidate for FAIR principles implementation in a laboratory context. The principle of Findability states that in order to be findable an object must be easily retrievable by both humans and machines; in the case of NeXus data format, this is achieved through a rich set of embedded metadata and the use of a standardized vocabulary, which together facilitate efficient indexing, discovery, and retrieval of data across systems. Accessibility is supported by the fact that since these files are based on a HDF5 infrastructure, which is an open format, there is no need to use proprietary software or other resources to read or write them. The `h5py` library for Python and `libhdf5` for C programming language are among the available open source tools designed to read and write the NeXus files. In addition, online tools like the `myHDF5` web application developed by the Proton and Neutron Open Science Cluster ² allow users to explore the contents of a HDF5 file and - by extension - a NeXus file - directly from any web browser without needing any external documentation and without requiring the data to be moved from the local machine. Thus, even in restricted-access contexts—such as proprietary experiments or datasets involving human subjects—NeXus facilitates transparent metadata discovery and structured access workflows, aligning with sub-principles A1.1 and A1.2. Interoperability, which—as discussed in Section 1.3—is closely linked to semantic aspects and the readability of both data and metadata, is achieved in NeXus through the use of standardized definitions developed using the NeXus Definition Language (NXDL). NXDL was designed to facilitate data exchange between scientists and software by formalizing the nomenclature and organization of information within NeXus files, ensuring that equivalent entities are represented consistently across datasets. Semantic consistency is further maintained through the ongoing collaborative efforts of an international scientific community, including institutions such as the FAIRmat consortium, which focuses on modeling emerging experimental techniques and new types of instrumentation via the development of specific Applica-

²<https://myhdf5.hdfgroup.org/>

tion Definitions. Moreover, compatibility with dedicated data analysis tools such as DAWN and PyMCA enables straightforward interpretation of NeXus files without the need for custom parsing routines, thus enhancing software interoperability and easing integration into analysis workflows. Reusability is guaranteed by a combination of its structured format, detailed metadata, and adherence to scientific standards. Having a rich set of metadata that thoroughly describes the experimental setup—including details about data provenance and acquisition methods—significantly enhances the reusability of the data in different contexts and enables users to fully understand the rationale behind an experiment. In NeXus, the ability to create explicit links between data and metadata within the file structure provides essential contextualization, reducing the risk of misinterpretation. Furthermore, the use of standardized data structures through specific NeXus classes—such as NXdata and NXinstrument—not only preserves internal consistency but also facilitates data reuse by users who may not have detailed knowledge of the original experimental setup. This structured, self-describing approach supports both long-term usability and interdisciplinary data sharing.

Chapter 3

When light meets matter: a brief introduction to spectroscopy

When thinking about spectra, the first thing that comes to mind is the famous experiment conducted by Isaac Newton in 1665. Newton isolated a single beam of white light by making a hole in the shutter of his study window and directed it onto a glass prism. The interaction between the beam and the prism revealed that white light is actually composed of a combination of various colors—that is, a spectrum. The results obtained by Newton are the precursors of what we now call spectroscopy: the branch of physics that deals with the interactions between electromagnetic radiation and matter. The study of these interactions is an extremely valuable tool for understanding the nature of chemical species and materials. At this point, it is natural to wonder how light and matter can interact with each other, and what kinds of information can be inferred from these phenomena. When electromagnetic radiation strikes an object, it can undergo different fates: it can be absorbed, re-emitted, or scattered. The various spectroscopic techniques not only differ in terms of the region of the electromagnetic spectrum they use, but also in the type of “fate” they examine. Each of these pathways can lead to different levels of understanding regarding the characteristics of a species and can provide different types of information about it. In the following sections, two spectroscopic techniques - transient absorption spectroscopy and photoluminescence spectroscopy - will be described, along with an experimental case study. These techniques exemplify how specific spectroscopic methods can be tailored to extract complementary information about the structure, composition, and behavior of materials.

3.1 Transient Absorption Spectroscopy

3.1.1 Investigation of Ultrafast Phenomena

All the processes that occur on a timescale of an order of magnitude less than 1 microsecond are defined ultrafast phenomena. Examples of these phenomena include the dynamics of hot carriers in semiconductors and photo-induced chemical reactions. Given the timescale involved, studying these processes requires a resolution time. Put simply, one of the components of the experimental setup must change faster than the process being analyzed. Since the light is the fastest object findable in nature, the most suitable analytical technique is spectroscopy, more specifically ultrafast spectroscopy. Indeed, in ultrafast spectroscopy the key factor that enables time resolution is the use of short laser pulses. The mode locking technique is used to obtain these pulses. Mode locking induces a phase difference between the longitudinal modes of an optical cavity. The longitudinal modes are sets of frequencies originated by the stationary waves in the laser optical cavity. Since these modes can interfere with each other, in order to avoid the destructive interference that could provoke fluctuations in the laser intensity, it is useful to establish a fixed phase relationship to produce periodic constructive interference which results in the generation of short laser pulses. Laser mode locking can be achieved using different methods, one of which, used in EuroFEL Support Laboratory, involves the use of oscillators where the Kerr effect is present. Even though the laser pulses obtained via mode-locking are theoretically suitable to carry out time-resolved spectroscopy experiments, it is necessary to amplify their energy. The amplification can be achieved by using the Chirped Pulse Amplification Technique. This technique is articulated in three steps: in the first one, the duration of the pulse is extended, reaching the picosecond timescale, then the stretched pulse is sent through a regenerative amplifier that increases its intensity. Subsequently, the pulse is compressed bringing its duration down to the femtoseconds timescale. The amplified pulse obtained with this method can be used to generate laser radiation with various energies thanks to an Optical Parametric Amplifier (OPA). The OPA allows fine-tuning of the laser wavelength through the use of nonlinear optical effects while simultaneously preserving the temporal duration of the pulse.

3.1.2 Pump-Probe Transient Absorption Spectroscopy

General Aspect and Experimental Setup

Fast Transient Absorption Spectroscopy (FTAS) is a pump-probe technique of time resolved spectroscopy that is useful to investigate the dynamics of ul-

trafast processes in various types of materials[8]. The principle behind FTAS is quite straightforward: a short laser pulse - the pump - is absorbed by the sample, causing its excitation then, after a brief delay of time, another laser pulse - the probe - is sent towards the sample in order to elicit information about the changes in its absorption due to the interaction with the pump. It is possible to follow the dynamics of the absorption change of the sample by modifying the delay time of the probe pulse with respect to the pump. The latter should be more intense than the probe in order to excite the sample, while the probe, since its function is the mere investigation of the excited sample, ideally should not interfere with it. In Figure 3.1 is sketched the typical experimental setup of a pump-probe experiment: the pulse generated by the Ti:Sapphire laser source is guided towards a beam splitter that divides it in two parts. While the first part is sent through an optical parametric amplifier that produces tunable pump pulses, the second part passes through a nonlinear medium, for example a fluorite (CaF_2) or a sapphire crystal, in order to generate the white light supercontinuum that is used as probe. It is possible to select the probe wavelength with a dispersion element such as a diffraction grid. The pump light and the probe light are then superimposed on the sample while the chopper blocks periodically the pump beam to allow to take the measurements after the interaction of the probe with the sample. Finally, the intensity of the probe pulse is collected by a CCD or by another suitable photon detector. As stated before, FTAS allows to study the time

Figure 3.1: Schematic illustration of a typical TAS setup.[9]

dependence of the absorption of a sample. The expression of the intensity of the probe pulse after the interaction with the excited sample is, according to the absorption law:

$$I_{\text{exc}} = I_0 \cdot 10^{-A_{\text{exc}}}$$

Where I_0 is the intensity of the incident pulse and A_{exc} is the absorption of the excited sample.

When the sample is not excited we can write, instead:

$$I_{steady\ state} = I_0 \cdot 10^{-A_{steady\ state}}$$

In order to obtain the difference in absorption, it is necessary to divide the equation of the excited state by the equation of the steady state and then take the logarithm:

$$\Delta A = A_{exc} - A_{steady\ state} = \log \left(\frac{I_{exc}}{I_{steady\ state}} \right)$$

This equation provides two useful insights: if we want to study the absorption changes it is not necessary to measure the intensity of the incident pulse and the signal measured with FTAS is nonetheless the absorption difference itself. Is it reasonable, therefore, to state that the difference of absorption measured in these experiments is a function of both the delay time between the pump and the probe and the probe wavelength.

Transient Absorption Spectra

A transient absorption spectra is the result of the contribution of the various phenomena that occurs when the sample interacts with the pump and the probe pulses. These phenomena are: Ground State Bleaching (GSB), Stimulated Emission (SE) and Excited State Absorption (ESA). As stated before, the pump pulse excites the sample, promoting its molecules from the ground state to an excited state. This promotion causes a decrease in the population of the ground state and, therefore, the disappearance of a part of the ground state absorption signal (GSA). In other words, the delta of the absorption at the wavelengths of the GSA is negative. This contribution to the spectra is therefore called Ground State Bleaching (GSB). The GSB is observable in a spectrum until all the excited electrons revert to their ground state. The Stimulated Emission is due to the interaction between the photons of the probe pulse and some of the molecules in the excited state. These molecules emit photons characterized by the same polarization, direction and wavelength as the photons emitted when the molecules return to their ground state. The contribute of the SE on the spectra, similarly to the contribute of GSB is negative because the emission of light is viewed as a negative absorption. The last contribute, the Excited State Absorption (ESA), arises from the fact that electrons are already in an excited state that can absorb photons and move towards excited states of higher energy. The IA contribute on the absorption is always positive.

FTAS spectroscopy is mainly interpreted as temporal dynamics of the population of excited states. In the transient absorption spectra are present

Figure 3.2: Schematic illustration of GSB, SE and ESA contributions in transient absorption spectroscopy.[10]

both coherent and incoherent dynamics mixed in terms of population and polarization effect. In general the incoherent part prevails after few picosecond allowing us to perform population analysis [11]. It is possible to acquire a collection of transient spectra with different pump-probe delay times in order to obtain a tridimensional transient map. The parameters that describe a transient map are: the pump-probe delay time (x-axis), the probe wavelength (y-axis) and the transient signal intensity indicated by a false color scale. The transient map contains all the information about the dynamics of the processes involved in the sample and allows us to perform detailed analysis by the extraction of the data at a given wavelength.

Figure 3.3: Example of a transient absorption map obtained by measuring spectra at different pump-probe delays.[12]

3.1.3 Photoluminescence Spectroscopy

Photoluminescence Spectroscopy (PL) is based on the emission of light by the recombination of carriers excited by the laser radiation from the ground energy level to levels with higher energies (photoexcitation). The photoexcitation is followed by various relaxation processes that may cause the emission of other photons (radiative process) or may not (nonradiative process). The energy of the emitted photons is correlated to the difference in energies of the electron states involved into the transition. In material science PL spectroscopy is a powerful tool for the characterization of the electrical properties of semiconductors. The luminescence is a linear technique, in its simplest interpretation is modeled only by the product of the population of the state involved [13]. Luminescence and pump-probe spectroscopy provide useful complementary information.

3.1.4 A case of study: characterization of halide perovskites via photoluminescence and transient absorption spectroscopy

As previously stated, Photoluminescence Spectroscopy and Transient Absorption Spectroscopy are powerful tools for the investigation of structural and electronic properties of materials. To demonstrate their practical application is useful to consider a series of experiments conducted on halide hybrid perovskite samples. Perovskite is a mineral composed by calcium titanate (CaTiO_3) that gave its name to a broader class of compounds with the same crystal formula ABX_3 where A and B are cations and X is an anion. The perovskite crystal structure is cubic and consists of a framework in which the B cations coordinate the A anions while the interstitial spaces are occupied by X anions.

A perovskite crystal structure is considered stable if the value of the ionic radius of the species involved satisfies the equation:

$$R_A + R_X = \sqrt{R_B + R_X} \cdot t$$

Where R_A, R_B and R_X are the radii and t is the tolerance factor. The cubic structure can be preserved only if the tolerance factor falls within the range 0.78-1.05.

In the context of this experiment, methylammonium lead chloride (MAPbCl_3) perovskites were synthesized. With respect to Figure 3.3, the methylammonium ions are indicated with the letter A, the lead cations with the letter B and the chloride anions with X.

Figure 3.4: Structural representation of a perovskite

The aim of the study was to investigate the effects of bromine substitution

on the structural and physical properties of these materials. By gradually replacing chlorine with bromine, we sought to understand how such compositional changes impact lattice stability, bandgap tuning, and charge carrier dynamic.

3.1.5 Description of the experiment

The starting point of the experiment was the synthesis of MAPbCl_3 via liquid deposition of the substrates - PbCl_2 and MACl - on glass and ITO glass supports in order to obtain a uniform layer of material. The anion substitution was achieved by dipping both the glass and the ITO glass supports in an isopropanol solution of MABr (methylammonium bromide). The dipping was carried out varying the exposure time of the supports to the IPA/ MABr solution to evaluate the extent of the anion substitution in the crystal lattice. The occurrence of the bromine substitution was verified through SEM imaging and X-Ray Diffraction analysis. The SEM images show that the structure obtained with this synthesis are nanocubes whose dimensions increase after the chlorine-bromine substitution. The X-Ray Diffraction analysis and the UV absorption proved that the anion substitution occurs almost immediately at short exposure times, such as 30 seconds. The XRD spectra shows also a shift of the (1 0 0) peak towards smaller angles related to the enlargement of the lattice parameter, that describes the unit distance between the unit cells of a crystal lattice. The analysis of absorption spectra shows also a progressive shift of the onset towards lower photon energies while in the photoluminescence spectra is easily observed the red shift of the peaks for the perovskites that underwent to increasing exposure times. The transient absorption spectra provide information about the carrier density and dynamics. It is evident that the value of k_2 related to the electron-hole radiative recombination process decrease with the bromine content.

(a) Photoluminescence spectra of samples for different dipping times

(b) Transient absorption spectra of samples for different dipping times

(c) X-ray diffraction spectra – shift of the (100) peak

(d) Trend of the recombination rate constant k_2 as a function of bromine concentration.

Figure 3.5: Spectroscopic Characterization of substituted hybrid halide perovskites

Chapter 4

The Laboratory Facility

The EuroFEL Support Laboratory (EFSL) participates in the offer of NFFA-DI project. Its experimental activities are focused on the study of ultrafast phenomena in nanostructured, plasmonic and photovoltaic materials by transient absorption spectroscopy and photoluminescence spectroscopy. The purpose of the laboratory is also to build up a spectroscopy community in Italy able to support the activities at Free Electron Laser facilities.

Figure 4.1 shows the experimental equipment used for pump-probe transient absorption experiments:

Figure 4.1: Transient Absorption Spectroscopy Experimental Equipment (courtesy of EuroFEL Support Lab)

The laser system consists of the following components:

- Ti:Sapphire Oscillator (Coherent Vitara-T)
- Regenerative Amplifier (Coherent Legend Elite H+)

- Optical Parametric Amplifier (OPA) (Coherent OPerA - Solo)

The Ti:Sapphire Oscillator generates laser pulses which wavelength is center at 800 nm. The pulses have a temporal duration of 20 femtoseconds, a repetition rate of 80 MHz, and an average power of 50 mW. The radiation produced by the oscillator is directed into the Regenerative Amplifier that generates pulses with a temporal duration of 35 fs, an energy of 4 mJ and a repetition rate of 1 KHz. Finally, the Optical Parametric Amplifier produces laser pulses of tunable wavelength in a range between 240 e 20000 nm with a temporal duration of 40 fs using the output radiation of the Regenerative Amplifier. The pulses obtained by the Optical Parametric Amplifier act as the pump in the context of transient absorption experiments.

Within the NFFA-DI project the acquired instrument is a high repetition rate ultrafast laser system tunable in photon wavelength. In this way it is possible to significantly reduce the energy per pulse and to access the linear regime in excitation that is the in operando regime of photovoltaic cells and optoelectronic devices.

The laser system is composed of an ultrafast source (Light Conversion CARBIDE 5W sp) at 1030 nm, about 170 fs pulse width, power 5 W, single-shot – 10 MHz repetition rate, and an Optical Parametric Amplifier OR-PHEUS with wavelength range 315 – 2600 nm with repetition rate up to 50 kHz. The commissioning of the laser system was performed using the pre-existing transient spectrometer.

The new laser system has allowed us to perform fast transient absorption spectroscopy experiments with excitation laser fluences down to 500 nJ/cm², with an extension toward the lower fluences.

Temperature dependent measurements can be performed in the 77 K (LNT)-RT range in high vacuum.

The experimental setup for the photoluminescence beamline is schematized in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Photoluminescence Experimental Setup[14]

The light sources are laser diodes that generate continuous wavelength radiation at 405 nm, which is used for steady-state photoluminescence measurements. For time-resolved photoluminescence, laser diodes emitting at 405 nm and 635 nm are employed, with a pulse duration of 12 ps and a repetition rate of up to 100 kHz. The photoluminescence emitted from the sample is collected by a HORIBA Jobin Yvon - iHR320 monochromator and is detected in the wavelength range of 400-1000 nm (CW and 80 MHz). The overall spatial resolution is around 100 micron. It is also possible to carry out temperature-dependent experiments using a high-vacuum cryostat which allows for a variable temperature range from 10 K to 400 K.

Chapter 5

Implementation of FAIR principles

5.1 State-Of-The-Art before FAIR implementation

Since its establishment, the EuroFEL Support Laboratory has been involved in the development of solutions aimed at simplifying routine activities for both the staff and guest scientists who wish to conduct experiments at the facility. The data management policy adopted by the staff relies heavily on cloud storage across multiple platforms, in synergy with backups on external hard drives.

There are two main reasons behind this approach. First, cloud storage enables designated users to access data freely on their devices from anywhere. Second, storing results in multiple environments provides a fail-safe mechanism to prevent data loss.

The cloud platforms currently in use include Google Drive (part of Google Workspace), OneDrive, and ownCloud. While the first two are proprietary, the latter is a free and open-source software. Data and other relevant materials are organized in folders, each categorized based on the type of experiment or activity.

The details of experimental activities are recorded in laboratory notebooks, referred to as *Logbooks* in EFSL terminology. Logbooks are Google Document files stored in designated folders within the laboratory's Google Drive. Each Logbook is named according to the category of the experiment and is structured in tables that provide a clear overview at a glance. Figure 5.1 shows an example of a Logbook entry related to a Femtosecond Transient Absorption Spectroscopy (FTAS) experiment on a halide perovskite

sample.

Figure 5.1: Logbook entry for a FTAS measurement (courtesy of EuroFEL Support Lab)

The table is divided into two parts: on the left is general information about the experimental conditions, while the right side shows a screenshot of the acquired spectrum. The information in the left column is very concise and includes the name of the sample, the pump wavelength, polarization of the electromagnetic radiation, exposure time, and acquisition mode (transmission). As shown in Figure 5.1, the logbook layout is simple and direct. However, it is worth noting that users unfamiliar with EFSL terminology or the specific experimental techniques may find the entries challenging to interpret.

A further example of a Logbook, illustrating the synthesis steps for a sample, is shown in Figure 5.2.

EFSL EuroFEL Support Laboratory	Sample: Nanostrutture di perovskiti Measure Info: SEM, EDX, FTAS, PL, ecc	Created: 16/01/2024
<p>Preparativa: sono stati utilizzati due processi.</p> <p>Processo 1, preso da DOI: 10.1039/c7tc03939e. Si utilizzano due soluzioni: a) MACl in DMF; b) PbCl₂ in DMF; (per molarità vedere schede campione). Procedimento a singolo step:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Si prepara una soluzione in rapporto 1:1 della sol_a e sol_b sopra spiegate, una goccia di quest'ultima si deposita sul substrato e si lascia a evaporare all'interno di un beaker contenente toluene, per almeno 12 h sotto cappa. <p>Processo 2, preso da DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b03965. Si utilizzano due soluzioni: a) MACl in un soluzione di IPA con 10%v di DMF; b) PbCl₂ in DMF; (per molarità vedere schede campione). Procedimento a due step:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deposizione di gocce della soluzione di PbCl₂ fino a completa copertura del substrato, a seguire si asciuga il solvente in eccesso lasciando su piastra a circa 100°C; 2. Si immerge il substrato con PbCl₂ nella soluzione di MACl, a seguito si lava il campione con IPA per tre volte, per togliere il solvente in eccesso e lo si fa asciugare su piastra a circa 60°C/70°C. <p>Per ogni campione realizzato sono riportate le soluzioni utilizzate.</p> <p>Sostituzione Cl->Br</p> <p>La sostituzione viene eseguita immergendo i supporti su cui è stato sintetizzato MAPbCl₃ in una soluzione 0.05 M di MABr in IPA. Sono stati quindi scelti differenti tempi di dipping in maniera tale da osservare la variazione del grado di sostituzione dell'anione bromuro nella struttura della perovskite con il cloruro.</p> <p>_____</p> <p>I pesi molecolari sono rispettivamente:</p> <p>-MACl = 67.52 g/mol -PbCl₂= 278.1 g/mol</p>		

Figure 5.2: Logbook entry for the synthesis of hybrid halide perovskite samples (courtesy of EuroFEL Support Lab)

Experimental data acquired from the beamlines are generally visualized and processed using proprietary software such as OriginLab and MATLAB. To comply with FAIR principles, the laboratory has chosen to convert the output of the photoluminescence and femtosecond transient absorption beamlines into the NeXus format.

5.2 NXoptical_spectroscopy Application Definition

Before delving into the technical aspects of the various workflows, it is necessary to briefly describe the NeXus application definition used for the development of the files for EFSL. As discussed in Chapter 2, NeXus files are organized in a way that allows to describe in every detail the experiment carried out, with respect to data and metadata. In order to have a precise description compliant with NeXus standard, each experiment must be categorized by its appropriate Application Definition. FAIRmat consortium has contributed to the development of several NeXus Application Definitions designed to describe specific categories of experiments commonly conducted in the field of materials science. NXoptical_spectroscopy[15] is among them. As stated on the documentation website, NXoptical_spectroscopy is “a general application definition of optical spectroscopy elements, which may be used as a template

to derive specialized optical spectroscopy experiments”. While allowing for significant customization, the backbone of `NXoptical_spectroscopy` remains structured around the elements already discussed in Chapter 2: `NXentry`, `NXinstrument`, `NXsample` and `NXdata`. The `NXentry` group serves as the top-level container for an experiment within a NeXus file. It generally includes key metadata such as the experiment title, timestamps, sample information, instrument settings, application definition used and references to the data acquisition results. `NXinstrument` contains all the metadata related to the description of the spectroscopy instrumental setup, such as electromagnetic radiation sources (categorized in `beam_type` and `source_type`), monochromator and other optical components. The `NXsample` group is dedicated to the information related to the sample that undergoes the experiment, containing metadata such as the name, the `chemical_formula` and the `physical_form`. Finally, the `NXdata` is used to archive both the raw and processed data acquired from the experiment.

NeXus Group	Description
<code>NXentry</code>	Top-level container of the NeXus file. Contains general metadata such as experiment title, start and end times, application definition name and experiment type.
<code>NXinstrument</code>	Describes the experimental setup and components used, such as the radiation source (with beam type and source type), monochromator, detector, and other optical elements.
<code>NXsample</code>	Contains metadata related to the sample under study, including sample name, chemical formula, physical form, and other relevant physical properties.
<code>NXdata</code>	Holds the numerical data recorded during the experiment. Both raw and processed data arrays are included, often linked to corresponding axes such as wavelength or intensity.

Table 5.1: Main NeXus groups used in `NXoptical_spectroscopy` and their contents.

5.3 Workflow for Transient Absorption Spectroscopy Beamline

The Transient Absorption Spectroscopy beamline operates thanks to a software written by Dr. Daniele Catone, head of EuroFEL Support Laboratory,

in LabVIEW. LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrumentation Engineering Workbench) is an integrated development environment (IDE) for the G programming language, produced and distributed by National Instruments under a proprietary license. This environment allows developers to write code in an unique way by using icons and other graphic objects connected by wires to define a dataflow, as illustrated in Figure 5.3. The dataflow, in turn, represents the sequence of operations that the user intend to execute in order to obtain a certain result.

Figure 5.3: LabVIEW code example (credits: Wikipedia)

The LabVIEW Acquisition Interface for the FTAS beamline generates data files in ASCII format, more specifically .dat files. A typical .dat file for Transient Absorption Spectroscopy consists in a matrix, where the first row and first column —excluding the top-left element—represent the probe wavelength and the pump-probe delay times, respectively. The remaining values in the core of the matrix correspond to the transient absorption signal. Since this interface allows to generate directly HDF5 files, the workflow for this beamline is articulated in the following steps:

1. Reading the .dat file
2. Selection of NXoptical_spectroscopy groups and classes for describing transient absorption spectroscopy experiments
3. Integration of NXoptical_spectroscopy groups and classes in the LabVIEW interface dataflow
4. Testing the updated dataflow during measurement sessions

5.3.1 Reading of .dat Files and Selection of NXoptical_spectroscopy Groups and Classes

The first operation I performed was to write a Python script to open the .dat file and convert it into a test NeXus file, in order to get a general idea of what the output would look like. Secondly, since—as previously mentioned—the LabVIEW-based interface is capable of automatically generating files in HDF5 format, a set of entries from the NXoptical_spectroscopy application definition was selected in agreement with the EFSL staff. The experimental data and metadata from this beamline were also jointly reviewed with Giovanni Gallerani, a fellow student from the Master’s program who worked with UDynI research group (CNR-IFN, Milan) on a similar transient absorption equipment, in an effort to align our approaches and develop a common description of the experiment. An overview of the selected entries is shown in Appendix B, Table B.1. The high degree of customization offered by this application definition made it possible to thoroughly structure the specific features of this type of experiment. Particular attention was devoted to the organization of the experimental data, which were categorized into the `data` and `raw_data` classes.

In the `data` class, the elements of the matrix from the .dat file were extracted and categorized as wavelength, delay time, and signal intensity. The `raw_data` class contained, as also reported in the `experiment_description` group, the following data:

- `Ref_Pump` – Probe spectrum acquired by the reference monochromator (equipped with a CCD) when the sample is excited by the pump.
- `Ref_NoPump` – Probe spectrum acquired by the reference monochromator (equipped with a CCD) when the sample is not excited by the pump.
- `Sample_Pump` – Probe spectrum transmitted/reflected by the sample and acquired by the monochromator (equipped with a CCD) when the sample is excited by the pump.
- `Sample_NoPump` – Probe spectrum transmitted/reflected by the sample and acquired by the monochromator (equipped with a CCD) when the sample is not excited by the pump.

5.3.2 Integration of NXoptical_spectroscopy groups and classes in the LabVIEW interface dataflow and test phase

The LabVIEW dataflow was updated in collaboration with Dr. Daniele Catone with the groups selected from the application definition. These updates are also reflected in the user interface, which, as shown in the figure, includes a selectable checkbox that allows the user to directly generate the NeXus file. The new features were tested during the laboratory's routine measurement sessions. We verified that NeXus files are generated without issues, and an example of the results obtained is shown in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.4: LabVIEW User Interface (courtesy of EuroFEL Support Laboratory)

Figure 5.5: Detail of the updated LabVIEW dataflow (courtesy of EuroFEL Support Laboratory)

Figure 5.6: Example of a NeXus file obtained after the dataflow update

5.4 Workflow for Photoluminescence Beamline

Whereas the Transient Absorption Spectrometer produces a single output file in ASCII format, the Photoluminescence Spectrometer generates two separate files in different formats: one in `.spc` and the other in `.txt`

The `.spc` format was developed by Galactic Industries in 1986 for storing spectroscopic data. Today, it is widely adopted by optical instrument manufacturers, who use it as the output format for their data acquisition software. Since it is a binary format, it cannot be read with a standard text

editor and requires specialized software or readers. Despite this limitation, the `.spc` format offers the advantage of containing not only the spectral analysis data—such as wavelengths and intensity counts—but also the metadata related to the instrument setup, e.g. the incident laser wavelength and grating step size. On the other hand, the `.txt` file contains only the raw data (wavelength and intensity).

As a result, the `.spc` file is the ideal candidate for the direct generation of NeXus files. The EFSL group’s request is to automate the generation of NeXus files from the spectrometer’s output using a dedicated graphical interface. The workflow for this beamline is organized into the following steps:

1. Reading the `.spc` file
2. Extraction of data and metadata
3. Preparation of NeXus file entries for the graphical interface
4. Development of the graphical interface based on the requirements from step 3
5. Testing of the interface on various devices and operating systems

5.4.1 Reading of `.spc` files

In order to identify the type and amount of data and metadata produced during a spectrometer run, it was necessary to open the generated `.spc` file. As illustrated in the previous paragraph, this type of file cannot be opened with standard text editors. Therefore, I used the `spc` Python module developed by Rohan Isaac¹. As described on the GitHub page, this module not only extracts header information from the `.spc` file into Python objects, but also allows for the generation of plots from the retrieved data. Metadata contained within the file can be accessed using dedicated functions.

¹<https://github.com/rohanisaac/spc>

```
[1]: import spc
      f = spc.File('/Users/lauracostantini/virtual_4/PL_spc_files/Pass_12K_100sl_1s_0p1uW.spc')
      f.log_dict

x-y(1)
[1]: {b'ACQ. TIME (S) ': b' 1',
      b'ACCUMULATIONS ': b' 1',
      b'RANGE (NM) ': b' 600...750',
      b'WINDOWS ': b' 2',
      b'AUTOFOCUS ': b' OFF',
      b'AUTOEXPOSURE ': b' OFF',
      b'SPIKE FILTER ': b' SINGLE ACCUM. (SIZE',
      b'DELAY TIME (S) ': b' 0',
      b'BINNING ': b' 1',
      b'READOUT MODE ': b' SIGNAL',
      b'DENOISE ': b' OFF',
      b'ICS CORRECTION ': b' OFF',
      b'DARK CORRECTION ': b' OFF',
      b'INST. PROCESS ': b' OFF',
      b'DETECTOR TEMPERATURE (\xb0C) ': b' -60.1',
      b'INSTRUMENT ': b' OSD',
      b'DETECTOR ': b' SYNCERITY',
      b'OBJECTIV ': b' X10',
      b'GRATING ': b' 600 / 750',
      b'EXCIT_LINE ': b' 405',
      b'FRONT ENTRANCE SLIT ': b' 98',
      b'FRONT EXIT SLIT ': b' 2000',
      b'EXIT MIRROR ': b' SIDE',
      b'STAGEXY ': b' MANUAL STAGE',
      b'X (\xb5M) ': b' 0',
      b'Y (\xb5M) ': b' 0',
      b'FULL TIME(S) ': b' 4',
      b'PROJECT ': b' 2025005_ELHAM_CSPBIBR',
      b'SAMPLE ': b' CSPBIBR',
      b'SITE ': b' 300 K',
      b'TITLE ': b' PASS_12K_100SL_1S_0P1UW',
      b'REMARK ': b' 100 UW',
      b'DATE ': b' 05.03.2025 16:20'}
```

Figure 5.7: Set of metadata extracted with spc module

Figure 5.4 shows the result of exploring an `.spc` file from a photoluminescence measurement. As clearly shown, all instrument-related metadata are stored in a Python dictionary. However, a limitation of the module is that it is currently not compatible with the latest stable version of Python.

5.4.2 Extraction of data and metadata, preparation of the NeXus File

Before proceeding with the development of the graphical user interface, I wrote a Python script that, by integrating the `spc` module, extracted useful data and metadata, which were then incorporated into the framework of a NeXus file specific to photoluminescence. The application definition used for the NeXus file is, similarly to the case of FTAS, `NXoptical_spectroscopy`.

The processing of the test NeXus file served two purposes: the first was to standardize the description of the photoluminescence experiments in accordance with the spectrometer output, and the second was to formalize a set of instructions for the graphical user interface, enabling direct conversion from the `.spc` format to the `.nxs` format.

5.4.3 GUI development and test phase

I carried out the development of the graphical user interface (GUI) using the open-source library wxPython². This library allows the creation of graphical user interfaces across Windows, Linux, and macOS systems. The result is an interface that enables the user to select a starting folder from which they can choose individual .spc files or entire batches, and a destination folder where the resulting .nxs files from the conversion will be saved. I designed the interface layout to provide the user with an intuitive and seamless experience. An excerpt of the code is provided in Appendix A. As highlighted in section 5.1, since the spc module is not compatible with the latest version of Python, I used the pyinstaller³ package to make the application independent from the Python version installed on the device. In other words, even users who do not have the Python compiler installed on their computers can use this application, as it has no dependencies on the Python version in use.

Figure 5.8: GUI in action on MacOS

Testing was conducted on MacBook Air devices running the latest version of macOS Sequoia (which come with Python pre-installed) and on both

²<https://www.wxpython.org/>

³<https://pypi.org/project/pyinstaller/>

desktop and laptop devices supporting Windows 10 and 11, some of which do not have Python installed. In all cases, no differences in behavior were observed either in the graphical interface or in the output of the `.nxs` files. An example of a GUI generated `.nxs` is shown in Figure 5.9

Figure 5.9: Example of a NeXus file generated by the GUI

5.5 Issues

The difficulties encountered mainly relate to two areas: programming and the selection of data and metadata to be included in the NeXus files.

Regarding the coding aspect, the main challenge was learning how to write efficient and concise code, as well as delving into the development of graphical user interfaces. The selection of data and metadata for inclusion in the NeXus files proved complex, as the `NXoptical_spectroscopy` application definition itself provides a wide range of optional metadata groups that could be filled. This extensive range made it impossible to include them all indiscriminately, both in the LabVIEW interface and in the graphical user interface (GUI) for photoluminescence (PL). As a result, careful consideration was required to select a sensible subset of metadata to include.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

The FAIR principles represent a pathway toward enabling a paradigm shift, interpreted in a Kuhnian sense, in favor of Open Science. By promoting practices that enhance data Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, these principles aim to redefine the scientific workflow, emphasizing transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration, as also highlighted by the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

One of the key tools for implementing these principles is the NeXus data format, a particular data format built on top of the HDF5 file format, which is the result of a collaborative effort by a community of scientists and software developers representing major scientific facilities. Its primary goal is to facilitate greater cooperation in the analysis and visualization of data from a broad range of experiments.

The EuroFEL Support Laboratory, which is part of the infrastructure offered by the NFFA-DI project, has chosen to adopt the NeXus format for data generated by its ultrafast transient absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy beamlines.

In this thesis project, my efforts focused on adapting both the experimental data and the metadata structure to align with the NeXus standard, particularly by integrating the `NXoptical_spectroscopy` application definition, developed by the FAIRmat consortium to describe optical spectroscopy experiments. This allowed for the representation of both raw and processed data, as well as metadata, in a structured, semantically rich, and machine-readable form—thereby supporting the long-term objectives of FAIR data management by enabling standardized, interoperable, and reusable formats directly at the acquisition level.

For the transient absorption spectroscopy beamline the adaptation was technically straightforward: the existing LabVIEW acquisition software developed by the head of laboratory already supported HDF5 output. There-

fore, the update simply involved modifying the dataflow to include the groups and classes defined in `NXoptical_spectroscopy` suitable for the description of both the experiment and the equipment.

For the photoluminescence beamline I developed a cross-platform graphical user interface through which, given the `.spc` files acquired by the spectrometer as input, NeXus files can be generated directly. The `NXoptical_spectroscopy` application definition was also used for this type of experiment, ensuring consistency in data structuring and metadata representation across different spectroscopy techniques.

The NeXus files generated during measurement sessions were successfully visualized using open-source tools such as the web-based resource `myHDF5`, thereby confirming their interoperability across different platforms and operating systems.

Appendix A

GUI code excerpt

In this appendix, code excerpts from the Graphical User Interface developed for the generation of NeXus files for photoluminescence measurements are presented. All source code is publicly available in the official GitHub repository of the Master's program in Data Management and Curation https://github.com/Master-Data-Management-and-Curation/Thesis_Code/tree/main/cnr-ism.rm

```
1 import wx
2 import os
3 import threading
4 import h5py
5 import spc
6 from pathlib import Path
7 from datetime import datetime
8
9 class ConversionApp(wx.Frame):
10     def __init__(self, parent, title):
11         super().__init__(parent, title=title, size=(600,
12             500))
13         self.SetSizeHints(600, 500, 600, 500)
14         self.panel = wx.Panel(self)
15         self.sizer = wx.BoxSizer(wx.VERTICAL)
16         self.select_folder_btn = wx.Button(self.panel,
17             label="Select folder with .spc files")
18         self.select_folder_btn.Bind(wx.EVT_BUTTON, self.
19             on_select_folder)
20         self.sizer.Add(self.select_folder_btn, 0, wx.ALL,
21             10)
22         self.file_listbox = wx.CheckListBox(self.panel,
23             size=(600, 150))
```

```
19     self.sizer.Add(self.file_listbox, 0, wx.ALL, 10)
20     self.select_all_btn = wx.Button(self.panel, label
21         ="Select all files")
22     self.select_all_btn.Bind(wx.EVT_BUTTON, self.
23         on_select_all)
24     self.sizer.Add(self.select_all_btn, 0, wx.ALL,
25         10)
26     self.select_output_btn = wx.Button(self.panel,
27         label="Select output folder")
28     self.select_output_btn.Bind(wx.EVT_BUTTON, self.
29         on_select_output_folder)
30     self.sizer.Add(self.select_output_btn, 0, wx.ALL,
31         10)
32     self.output_folder_text = wx.TextCtrl(self.panel,
33         style=wx.TE_READONLY | wx.TE_MULTILINE, size
34         =(300, 35))
35     self.sizer.Add(self.output_folder_text, 0, wx.ALL
36         | wx.EXPAND, 10)
37     self.progress_bar = wx.Gauge(self.panel, range
38         =100, size=(600, 25))
39     self.sizer.Add(self.progress_bar, 0, wx.ALL, 10)
40     self.convert_btn = wx.Button(self.panel, label="
41         Start Conversion")
42     self.convert_btn.Bind(wx.EVT_BUTTON, self.
43         on_convert)
44     self.sizer.Add(self.convert_btn, 0, wx.ALL, 10)
45     self.panel.SetSizer(self.sizer)
46     self.Show()
47     self.input_folder = ""
48     self.output_folder = ""
49     self.update_output_folder_text()
50     self.files_to_convert = []
51
52     def on_select_folder(self, event):
53         dialog = wx.DirDialog(self, "Select a folder",
54             style=wx.DD_DEFAULT_STYLE)
55         if dialog.ShowModal() == wx.ID_OK:
56             self.input_folder = dialog.GetPath()
57             self.files_to_convert = [f for f in os.
58                 listdir(self.input_folder) if f.endswith('
59                 .spc')]
60             self.file_listbox.Clear()
61             self.file_listbox.Append(self.
```

```
        files_to_convert)
47     dialog.Destroy()
48
49     def on_select_output_folder(self, event):
50         dialog = wx.DirDialog(self, "Select output folder
51             ", style=wx.DD_DEFAULT_STYLE)
52         if dialog.ShowModal() == wx.ID_OK:
53             self.output_folder = dialog.GetPath()
54             self.update_output_folder_text()
55             dialog.Destroy()
56
57         def update_output_folder_text(self):
58             self.output_folder_text.SetValue(self.
59                 output_folder if self.output_folder else "No
60                 output folder selected")
61
62         def on_convert(self, event):
63             selected_files = [self.files_to_convert[i] for i
64                 in range(len(self.files_to_convert)) if self.
65                 file_listbox.IsChecked(i)]
66             if not selected_files:
67                 wx.MessageBox("Select at least one file to
68                     convert", "Error", wx.OK | wx.ICON_ERROR)
69                 return
70             if not self.output_folder:
71                 wx.MessageBox("Select an output folder", "
72                     Error", wx.OK | wx.ICON_ERROR)
73                 return
74             self.convert_btn.Disable()
75             self.thread = threading.Thread(target=self.
76                 convert_files, args=(selected_files,))
77             self.thread.start()
```

Listing A.1: GUI-based SPC to NeXus Converter

Appendix B

NXoptical_spectroscopy groups and classes

Table B.1 presents the groups and classes selected from the available definitions within `NXoptical_spectroscopy` to describe the two beamlines. The Transient Absorption Spectroscopy beamline was further customized by structuring the raw data as detailed in Section 5.3.1. Additional custom groups were also implemented for this beamline, including scan count and delay line parameters.

Group	Description	Fields
NXentry	Top-level container for the NeXus file, including general metadata about the experiment.	definition, experiment_description, experiment_type, experiment_subtype, end_time
NXdata	Contains the primary data and associated axes.	wavelength, axes, signal
NXinstrument	Describes the experimental setup and components used.	beam_type, source_type, incident_wavelength, incident_polarization, monochromator, entrance_slit, exit_slit, pulse_energy, parameter_reliability, count_type, channel_type, detector_type, fluence, linear_beam_sample_polarization
NXsample	Contains metadata related to the sample under study.	sample_name, chemical_formula, temperature
NXuser	Information about the user conducting the experiment.	name, affiliation, email

Table B.1: Overview of main NeXus groups and their associated fields in the NXoptical_spectroscopy application definition.

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